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On-Line First

2021 – 2023 RSIG Research Day Keynote Addresses and Invited Speakers

2021 Keynote Speaker

Emerging from the Cracks: Strengthening Our Place in a Post-COVID World

Dr. Madeline Burghardt

Instructor, Department of Critical Disability Studies, Department of Development Studies, Department of Music, York University; Instructor, Department of Disability Studies, King's College, University of Western Ontario

The COVID-19 pandemic has revealed the depth of the gaps in the social support systems ostensibly designed to care for more vulnerable members of our communities, as well as the degree to which institutional models of care continue to dominate the lives of people with intellectual disabilities in Ontario. In this talk, I present what we have learned about the place of marginalized people in Ontario as we begin to emerge from the destruction of the COVID-19 pandemic and call us to a commitment of agitation and activism towards creating a more just and equitable society in the post-COVID world.

2022 Keynote Speaker

Inclusive Research: Why it Takes More Than a Seat at the Table

Dr. Virginie Cobigo

Associate Professor, School of Psychology, University of Ottawa; Research Chair in Children and Youth Mental Health, CHEO Research Institute; Founding Director, Open Collaboration for Cognitive Accessibility

Please grab a chair and join our conversation on how to engage persons with intellectual and developmental disabilities in research. We will discuss best practices in inclusive research with persons with intellectual and developmental disabilities. These best practices include strategies to make research processes and methods accessible and to respect the autonomy of the people we want to engage in research. We will also discuss ways to build reciprocity and trust between researchers and persons with a range of cognitive abilities.

2022 Invited Panel

Self-Advocates Experiences, Perspectives and Recommendations on Inclusive Research Practices

Ashlee Dagenais, Crystal Silverthorne, Zhade & Lana, Courtney Bishop & Dr. Laura Mullins, Brock University

This panel discussion will explore the experiences of self-advocates during an inclusive research process. Self-advocates will be asked pre-determined questions about a photovoice research process, Voices Lost in Crisis, to provide insight on best inclusive research practices from the perspective of collaborators with disabilities. The participatory action research (PAR) project being discussed highlighted self-advocates' lived experience in the COVID-19 pandemic. Through hearing self-advocates discuss their experiences with the Voices Lost in Crisis project, attendees will learn about preferred ways to engage persons with IDD throughout the research process as collaborators in a meaningful, accessible, and inclusive way.

2023 Keynote Speaker

Collectively Creating Conditions of Knowing: The Offerings of an Activist-Art Project Series called Into the Light

Dr. Evadne Kelly

Re•Vision: The Centre for Art and Social Justice, University of Guelph

In this presentation, Dr. Kelly will share aspects of her work that relate to the theme “*Knowledge is Power: Creative and Collaborative Ways of Sharing Knowledge.*” Specifically, she will speak about working from her archival research to lead and collectively create a project series called Into the Light. Into the Light is an activist-art project series that addresses histories of Ontario educational institutions producing and disseminating oppressive knowledge and traces those histories to present day inequities and works to counter them.

The project is guided by the wisdom of Mona Stonefish, of the Anishinaabeg Three Fires Confederacy, and Respecting Rights members Peter Park, Marie Slark, and Antoinette Charlebois. Stonefish, Park, Slark, and Charlebois are survivor-activists who share their stories of surviving and fighting against the horrors of eugenics. They wish for everyone to learn about the devastating effects of eugenics on all of us.

In Ontario, eugenics (a faulty pseudo-science focused on “race betterment” through heredity) created the conditions for dehumanization and devaluing difference. It spawned policies and practices that targeted First Nations and settler people who did not fit white settler colonial worldviews, including Black people and other racialized groups as well as poor, disabled,

labelled-as-disabled, and LGBTQ+ people through institutional confinement, restrictive marriage and immigration laws, assimilation, and coercive sterilization.

To expose these histories and intervene in their present-day forms, Dr. Kelly worked with a large team of First Nations, Métis, and Black, racialized, white, disabled, labelled-as-disabled, verbal, non-verbal, and non-disabled settler contributors to co-create accessible teaching and learning spaces that expand understandings of vitality and advance social justice. Our co-creation work to build a museum exhibition and a knowledge platform draws on decolonizing theories and methods of building solidarity, grounded in difference, between those who are unevenly implicated in colonialism (Gaztambide-Fernández 2012) to co-create new possibilities for the future.